

S1 Text: Supporting information**TOOTH MORPHOLOGY ELUCIDATES SHARK EVOLUTION ACROSS THE END-CRETACEOUS MASS EXTINCTION**

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CONTENTS

This PDF file includes:

Supplementary Methods and Results

Supplementary Tables

Tables A–VV

Supplementary Figures

Figures A–DD

Other Supplementary Materials for this manuscript include the following:

S1 Data: Global Occurrence Database (.xlsx)

S2 Data: 2D-Landmark Coordinate Data (.tps)

S3 Data: Sliders File (.txt)

S4 Data: Measurement Error Landmark Coordinate Data (.tps)

S5 Data: Annotated R Markdown File (.pdf)

S6 Data: ReadMe File (.txt)

S1 Code: R Markdown File (.rmd)

S2 Code: R Function (.r)

S3 Code: R Function (.r)

S4 Code: R Function (.r)

S5 Code: R Function (.r)

S6 Code: R Function (.r)

S7 Code: R Function (.r)

SUPPLEMENTARY METHODS

Measurement error. Digitization measurement error is often overlooked in geometric morphometric analyses, and can result in spurious interpretations [1,2]. We therefore quantified measurement error using an intra-class correlation coefficient, which equates to the ratio between repeated measures versus the total variation [2]. Computationally, this is undertaken as a one-way ANOVA. The proportion of measurement error is expressed as:

$$R = S_A^2 / (S_W^2 + S_A^2) \times 100$$

where S_A^2 (residual mean sum of squares) is the among-individuals variance, and S_W^2 (group sum of squares) is the within-individuals variance [2,3].

Heterodonty. The heterodont dentitions of sharks [4] can influence estimates of their disparity [5]. This is compounded by the usually isolated occurrences of fossil shark teeth, as well as positional variation along the jaw [6], and inconsistent anatomical terminology [4,6,7]. We therefore screened our literature-based image dataset to remove ambiguous descriptive terms (e.g., anterior/parasymphyseal) and inconsistent spelling (e.g., ‘symphyseal’ versus ‘symphysial’). We also treated ‘lateroanterior’ and ‘anterolateral’ as equivalents, but differentiated these from ‘lateroposterior’ and/or ‘posterolateral’. Our standardized categories thus included ‘anterior’, ‘anterolateral’, ‘commissural’, ‘intermediate’, ‘lateral’, ‘lateroposterior’, ‘parasymphyseal’, ‘posterior’, and ‘symphyseal’ (S1 Data).

Six disparity models were used for comparisons:

1. ‘Strict age model’. This provided a two-parameter model (Phenotype ~ Age) whereby the Procrustes variance was calculated for each time-bin (N=1198).
2. ‘Monognathic model’. This provided a three-parameter model (Phenotype ~ Age + Tooth Positions) whereby the Procrustes variance was calculated for each time-bin while accounting for variation in monognathic tooth positions (N=897).
3. ‘A dignathic model’. This provided a three-parameter model (Phenotype ~ Age + Jaw) whereby the Procrustes variance was calculated for each time-bin while accounting for variation in dignathic tooth positions (N=334).
4. ‘Combined model’. This provided a four-parameter model (Phenotype ~ Age + Tooth Positions + Jaw) whereby the Procrustes variance was calculated for each time-bin while accounting for both monognathic and dignathic variation (N=334).
5. ‘Validation model’. This provided a three-parameter model (Phenotype ~ Age + Tooth Positions) whereby the Procrustes variance was calculated for each time-bin while accounting for variation in monognathic tooth positions with all pre-assigned and ‘non-standardised’ tooth positions incorporated into the dataset (N=899).
6. ‘Monognathic and order model’. This provided a four-parameter model (Phenotype ~ Age + Tooth Positions + Orders) whereby the Procrustes variance was calculated for each time-bin while accounting for monognathic variation and order-level differences between time-bins (N=897).

Collecting bias. We observed a tendency towards larger tooth sizes being preferentially documented in our literature-based dataset. This was particularly evident among carchariids and odontaspids, which were represented mainly by ‘anterior’ and ‘lateral’ teeth indicating comparative under-sampling of their dimensionally smaller commissural dentition [6].

SUPPLEMENTARY RESULTS

Lagerstätten effects on disparity. Experimental exclusion of the Stevns Klint regional sub-sample (N=153) resulted in a non-significant (Table RR in S1 Text) increase in global disparity ($PV_{\text{Maastrichtian}}=0.073$; $PV_{\text{Danian-Selandian}}=0.079$; $p=0.547$) across the Maastrichtian–Danian–Selandian time-bins.

Lagerstätten effects on morphospace. Exclusion of the Stevns Klint regional sub-sample produced a significant morphospace shift on PC1–PC3 in the Maastrichtian–Danian time-bins irrespective of time-binning scheme (Table SS in S1 Text).

Effects of heterodonty on morphospace. General and axes-specific differences in morphospace were recovered for all monognathic heterodont tooth positions (Fig U in S1 Text, Tables TT and UU in S1 Text). On PC1, both ‘lateroposterior’ and ‘posterior’ tooth positions were negatively loaded, as opposed to the ‘parasymphyseal’ and ‘anterior’ tooth positions, which were positively loaded (Fig U in S1 Text). However, major overlap between all monognathic tooth positions are still visible. On PC2–PC4, the monognathic tooth position distributions were aligned, but with significant differences occurring on PC3 and PC4 (Fig U in S1 Text, panel C and D, Table UU in S1 Text). The effects of dignathic heterodonty were limited to PC2 and PC3 (Fig V in S1 Text, panel B and C). A clade-wise exploration of monognathic heterodonty indicated that tooth position differences were mainly evident along PC1 (Fig W in S1 Text). Furthermore, dignathic heterodonty principally affected lamniforms, hexanchiforms, as well as squaliforms to a lesser degree on PC1–PC4 (Fig W in S1 Text).

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES

Table A. Stratigraphic sub-divisions and corresponding sample sizes. Temporal age range (Ma) values are taken from the International Chronostratigraphic Chart v2020/03.

Era	Period	Age	Temporal range (Ma)	N _{selachimorpha}	N _{galeomorpii}	N _{squalmorpii}
Cenozoic	Paleogene	Thanetian	59.2 – 56.0	187	169	18
Cenozoic	Paleogene	Selandian	61.6 – 59.2	28	25	3
Cenozoic	Paleogene	Danian	66.0 – 61.6	209	177	32
Mesozoic	Cretaceous	Maastrichtian	72.1 ± 0.2 – 66.0	373	317	56
Mesozoic	Cretaceous	Campanian	83.5 – 72.1	359	336	23

Table B. Sample sizes and dataset proportions for each order-level clade, including †Synchodontiformes.

Taxon	Common name	Sample size (N)	Proportion (%)
Lamniformes	Mackerel Sharks	690	55.69
Carcharhiniformes	Ground Sharks	232	18.72
Orectolobiformes	Carpet Sharks	116	9.36
Heterodontiformes	Horn or Bullhead Sharks	23	1.86
Hexanchiformes	Cow and Frilled Sharks	43	3.47
Squaliformes	Dogfish Sharks	89	7.18
Echinorhiniformes	Bramble Sharks	6	0.48
Squatiformes	Angel Sharks	23	1.86
†Synchodontiformes	-	17	1.37
Total	-	1239	-

Table C. Time-binning schemes and sample sizes for galeomorph order-level clades.

Binning scheme	Time-bins	N _{lamniformes}	N _{carcharhiniformes}	N _{orectolobiformes}	N _{heterodontiformes}
Five-bin analysis	Campanian	276	34	17	6
	Maastrichtian	198	46	63	7
	Danian	64	80	21	4
	Selandian	23	2	0	0
	Thanetian	82	66	15	6
	Total	643	228	116	23
Four-bin analysis	Campanian	276	34	17	6
	Maastrichtian	198	46	63	7
	Danian-Selandian	104	82	21	4
	Thanetian	82	66	15	6
	Total	660	228	116	23

Table D. Time-binning schemes and sample sizes for squalomorph order-level clades, including †Synchodontiformes. Echinorhiniformes was excluded because of insufficient sample size. D-S = Danian-Selandian.

Disparity through time	Time-bins	N _{Hexanchiformes}	N _{squaliformes}	N _{squatiformes}	N _{synchodontiformes}
Five-bin analysis	Campanian	0	12	11	3
	Maastrichtian	5	40	5	3
	Danian	13	13	6	8
	Selandian	0	3	0	0
	Thanetian	14	3	1	0
	Total	32	71	22	14
Four-bin analysis	Campanian	0	12	11	3
	Maastrichtian	5	40	5	3
	D-S	21	31	6	10
	Thanetian	14	3	1	0
		Total	40	86	23

Table E. Time-binning schemes and sample sizes for superorder-level clades.

Disparity through time	Time-bins	N _{selachimorpha}	N _{galeomorphii}	N _{squalomorphii}	
Sub-stage level analysis	early Campanian	149	134	15	
	late Campanian	23	17	-	
	early Maastrichtian	98	86	12	
	late Maastrichtian	218	194	24	
	early Danian	80	61	19	
	middle Danian	80	76	-	
	late Danian	11	-	-	
		Total	659	568	70

Table F. Number, type and description of geometrically homologous fixed landmarks and sliding semi-landmarks. ‘Type 1’ and ‘Type 2’ designations refer to Bookstein [8].

Landmark	Description	Bookstein’s Typology
LM1	Junction of left cusp edge	Type 1
LM2	Junction of right cusp edge	Type 1
LM3	Cusp apex	Type 2
Curve	Description	Sliding semi-landmark
C1	Distal margin	N = 79
C2	Mesial margin	N = 81

Table G. Selected selachimorph tooth specimens used to assess digitization measurement error.

Order	Family	Genus	Species	Dental Unit	Specimen No.	Relative Position	Source
Lamniformes	Archaeolamnidae	<i>Archaeolamna</i>	<i>kopingensis judithensis</i>	upper	UM HBR 64	anterolateral	Cappetta 2012
Lamniformes	Otodontidae	<i>Cretolamna</i>	<i>maroccana</i>	upper	UM-BEG-C2.21	lateral	Cappetta <i>et al.</i> 2014b
Lamniformes	Odontaspidae	<i>Glueckmanotodus</i>	<i>heinzelini</i>	-	UM DOR 1	Posterior	Cappetta 2012
Lamniformes		<i>Palaeocarcharodon</i>	<i>orientalis</i>	-	-	anterior	Cappetta 2012
Lamniformes	Anacoracidae	<i>Squalicorax</i>	<i>africanus</i>	-	UM-CHA1-1	anterior	Bardet <i>et al.</i> 2000
Carcharhiniformes	Carcharhinidae	<i>Danogaleus</i>	<i>gueriri</i>	-	UM BOD 8	lateral	Cappetta 2012
Carcharhiniformes	Carcharhinidae	<i>Danogaleus</i>	<i>gueriri</i>	-	UM BOD 10	lateral	Cappetta 2012
Carcharhiniformes	Triakidae	<i>Palaeogaleus</i>	<i>navarroensis</i> nov sp.	-	AMNH 13710	lateral	Case & Cappetta 1997
Carcharhiniformes	Scyliorhinidae	<i>Scyliorhinus</i>	<i>monsaugustus</i> sp nov	-	MAO2-25	anterior	Guinot <i>et al.</i> 2013
Carcharhiniformes	Scyliorhinidae	<i>Scyliorhinus</i>	<i>monsaugustus</i> sp nov	-	MAO2-27	posterior	Guinot <i>et al.</i> 2013
Orectolobiformes	Hemiscylliidae	<i>Chiloscyllium</i>	<i>frequens</i> sp. nov.	-	P. 67019	anterior	Guinot <i>et al.</i> 2013
Orectolobiformes	Hemiscylliidae	<i>Chiloscyllium</i>	<i>frequens</i> sp. nov.	-	P. 67022	lateral	Guinot <i>et al.</i> 2013
Orectolobiformes	Hemiscylliidae	<i>Chiloscyllium</i>	<i>frequens</i> sp. nov.	-	P. 67020	lateroposterior	Guinot <i>et al.</i> 2013
Orectolobiformes	Ginglymostomatidae	<i>Plicatoscyllium</i>	<i>lehneri</i>	-	-	anterolateral	Cappetta 2012
Orectolobiformes	Ginglymostomatidae	<i>Plicatoscyllium</i>	<i>lehneri</i>	-	-	lateral	Cappetta 2012
Heterodontiformes	Heterodontidae	<i>Heterodontus</i>	<i>boussioni</i> sp nov	-	HAL2-7	lateral	Guinot <i>et al.</i> 2013
Heterodontiformes	Heterodontidae	<i>Heterodontus</i>	<i>creamridgensis</i>	-	WBR 95	anterior	Case & Cappetta 2004
Heterodontiformes	Heterodontidae	<i>Heterodontus</i>	<i>rugosus</i>	-	MGUH 29939	anterior	Adolfssen & Ward 2014
Heterodontiformes	Heterodontidae	<i>Heterodontus</i>	<i>rugosus</i>	-	MGUH 29941	lateral	Adolfssen & Ward 2014
Heterodontiformes	Heterodontidae	<i>Heterodontus</i>	sp. 2	-	MAO2-12	lateral	Guinot <i>et al.</i> 2013
Squaliformes	Somniosidae	<i>Centroscymnus</i>	<i>praecursor</i>	lower	MGUH 29910	-	Adolfssen & Ward 2014
Squaliformes	Squalidae	<i>Megasqualus</i>	<i>orpiensis</i>	-	UM MAR 6	anterior	Cappetta 2012
Squaliformes	Squalidae	<i>Megasqualus</i>	<i>orpiensis</i>	-	UM MAR 8	lateral	Cappetta 2012
Squaliformes	Squalidae	<i>Protosqualus</i>	<i>argentinensis</i> nov sp	-	MPM 10023	anterolateral	Bogan <i>et al.</i> 2016
Squaliformes	Squalidae	<i>Squalus</i>	<i>gabrielsoni</i>	-	MGUH 29901	lateral	Adolfssen & Ward 2014
Hexanchiformes	Hexanchidae	<i>Heptanchias</i>	sp	lower	LO 849 t	anterolateral	Siverson 1995
Hexanchiformes	Hexanchidae	<i>Notidanodon</i>	<i>loози</i>	lower	IRSNB P.1512	symphyseal	Cappetta 2012
Hexanchiformes	Hexanchidae	<i>Notidanodon</i>	sp.	upper	UM DAO 1-C	anterolateral	Cappetta 2012
Hexanchiformes	Hexanchidae	<i>Notidanodon</i>	sp.	upper	UM DAO 1-D	anterolateral	Cappetta 2012
Hexanchiformes	Hexanchidae	<i>Notorynchus</i>	sp.	upper	LO 848 t	anterolateral	Siverson 1995

Table H. Generalized Procrustes Analysis (GPA) with partial Procrustes superimposition. GPA was performed using different iterations to evaluate algorithm convergence. Q-values between 4.35–4.09 (iteration-level = 6 to 9) produced comparable alignment.

Fixed landmarks	Number of semi-landmarks	P	M	Q-value	GPA iterations	Sliding method
-	-	-	-	6.183326	3	BE
-	-	-	-	4.448685	4	BE
-	-	-	-	4.423181	5	BE
3	157 (sliders)	160	2D	4.357470	6	BE
-	-	-	-	4.297608	7	BE
-	-	-	-	4.207907	8	BE
-	-	-	-	4.098833	9	BE
-	-	-	-	3.959336	10	BE
-	-	-	-	3.785426	11	BE
-	-	-	-	3.584394	12	BE
-	-	-	-	3.350921	13	BE
-	-	-	-	3.098619	14	BE
-	-	-	-	2.827423	15	BE
-	-	-	-	2.543247	16	BE
-	-	-	-	2.261878	17	BE
-	-	-	-	1.989550	18	BE
-	-	-	-	1.964127	19	BE
-	-	-	-	1.335368	20	BE
-	-	-	-	1.658891	21	BE

BE = Minimized Bending Energy.

Table I. Repeatability of digitized landmarks. Shape variation = 99%; digitization and measurement error = ~1%.

	<i>d.f.</i>	SS	MS	R ²	F	Z	Pr(>F)
Individuals	29	3.9346	0.135674	0.98903	105.2969	14.5352	0.001
Replicates	1	0.0063	0.006258	0.00157	4.8565	3.0475	0.002
Residuals	29	0.0374	0.001288	0.00939			
Total	59	3.9782					

Table J. Principal Components Analysis (PCA) of the digitized landmark data. Computed variance (eigenvalues, λ_k) explained by the first 10 PC-axes (eigenvectors, u_k). PCA eigenvectors = 320.

Principal Component (u_k)	Standard Deviation (σ)	Proportion of Variance (%)	Cumulative Proportion
PC1	0.2222	61.736	0.6174
PC2	0.09869	12.180	0.73915
PC3	0.09269	10.743	0.84658
PC4	0.06080	4.623	0.89281
PC5	0.04459	2.487	0.91767
PC6	0.03464	1.500	0.93267
PC7	0.03248	1.319	0.94586
PC8	0.02645	0.875	0.95461
PC9	0.02395	0.717	0.96179
PC10	0.02238	0.626	0.96805

Table K. Descriptive and test statistics of order-level clades in morphospace.

PC-axis	Clade	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Median (\tilde{x})	Shapiro.W	Shapiro.p	Dip.Test.D	Dip.Test.p	Skewness
	Lamniformes								
1		690	0.07804863	0.070565597	0.9831824	4.002893e-07	0.01448571	0.4457993	0.14653437
2		690	-0.00306696	-0.001908225	0.9950210	2.456395e-02	0.01401653	0.5053166	-0.03982309
	Carcharhiniformes								
1		232	-0.0013767133	-0.034126110	0.9738609	0.0002750076	0.01769094	0.9306216	0.41108852
2		232	0.0004572805	-0.004317489	0.9926368	0.3021120732	0.03006935	0.1522842	-0.05334797
	Heterodontiformes								
1		23	-0.24043833	-0.19821966	0.8645787	0.005058779	0.10729258	0.02080989	-0.36321374
2		23	0.04587881	0.03401269	0.9748870	0.803614529	0.05664513	0.83150375	-0.05576618
	Orectolobiformes								
1		116	-0.08829770	-0.12129393	0.9289468	1.142309e-05	0.02086442	0.9906737	1.054916
2		116	0.02734313	0.04561915	0.9097573	9.223353e-07	0.02530561	0.9068080	-1.269113
	Hexanchiformes								
1		43	-0.2457358	-0.3389045	0.7663057	7.27881e-07	0.03307539	0.9905036	1.9166473
2		43	0.1390947	0.1739687	0.9295460	1.12184e-02	0.03845325	0.9360404	-0.7702537
	Squaliformes								
1		89	-0.21898115	-0.26686095	0.8973898	3.457211e-06	0.02559129	0.9733294	1.1367165
2		89	-0.06642451	-0.09510701	0.9370546	3.140320e-04	0.02268368	0.9920183	0.7381424
	Echinorhiniformes								
1		6	-0.2420685	-0.2445328	0.9680474	0.8790709	0.11510577	0.5867129	0.3005130
2		6	-0.1227031	-0.1954872	0.8429049	0.1377664	0.09042546	0.8364397	0.8304803
	Squatiniiformes								
1		23	-0.03117527	-0.01648834	0.9691875	0.66955901	0.07647978	0.3212052	-0.2157085
2		23	0.03056737	0.04240456	0.8140890	0.00064963	0.06131238	0.7174112	-1.3377591
	†Synchodontiformes								
1		17	0.07599271	0.008601875	0.9353278	0.266867293	0.09791731	0.1649063	0.05505126
2		17	0.03229257	0.091273980	0.8385699	0.007213756	0.07812923	0.5200557	-0.76225723

Table L. Procrustes Variance (PV) and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Selachimorpha (including †Synchodontiformes). Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Five-stage binning scheme					
Campanian	0.06911023	0.0627	0.0752	0.0687	0.0691
Maastrichtian	0.07584028	0.0693	0.0819	0.0754	0.0758
Danian	0.08275046	0.0727	0.0922	0.0821	0.0827
Selandian	0.04272476	0.0254	0.0566	0.0405	0.0415
Thanetian	0.08535443	0.0757	0.0943	0.0847	0.0853
Four-stage binning scheme					
Danian-Selandian	0.08439832	0.0754	0.0922	0.0835	0.0841

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table M. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Selachimorpha (excluding †Synchodontiformes) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Four-age time-binning scheme					
Campanian	0.06921892	0.0620	0.0757	0.0686	0.0691
Maastrichtian	0.07537421	0.0689	0.0818	0.0752	0.0756
Danian-Selandian	0.08217259	0.0739	0.0901	0.0818	0.0823
Thanetian	0.08535443	0.0752	0.0943	0.0844	0.0851

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table N. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Selachimorpha using the Stevns Klint regional sub-sample and a three-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Regional three-age time-binning scheme					
late Maastrichtian	0.09190902	0.0713	0.1097	0.0899	0.0911
early Danian	0.06939083	0.0566	0.0810	0.0684	0.0692
middle Danian	0.12391158	0.0871	0.1502	0.1176	0.1196

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table O. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Galeomorphii (including †Synchodontiformes) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Four-age time-binning scheme					
Campanian	0.06826546	0.0616	0.0747	0.0680	0.0684
Maastrichtian	0.06802529	0.0616	0.0741	0.0677	0.0681
Danian-Selandian	0.07309997	0.0655	0.0803	0.0727	0.0731
Thanetian	0.07741032	0.0674	0.0864	0.0766	0.0772

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table P. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Galeomorphii (excluding †Synchodontiformes) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Four-age time-binning scheme					
Campanian	0.06835569	0.0613	0.0748	0.0678	0.0683
Maastrichtian	0.06750400	0.0608	0.0739	0.0671	0.0676
Danian-Selandian	0.07009500	0.0625	0.0770	0.0695	0.0700
Thanetian	0.07741032	0.0682	0.0861	0.0769	0.0774

Table Q. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Squalomorphii using the four-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Four-age time-binning scheme					
Campanian	0.05885412	0.0399	0.0726	0.0558	0.0568
Maastrichtian	0.06656151	0.0504	0.0805	0.0650	0.0659
Danian-Selandian	0.07742955	0.0559	0.0962	0.0754	0.0767
Thanetian	0.05885900	0.0432	0.0682	0.0553	0.0561

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table R. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Galeomorphii (including †Synchodontiformes) using the Stevns Klint regional sub-sample and a three-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Regional three-age time-binning scheme					
late Maastrichtian	0.07965242	0.0551	0.0987	0.0762	0.0776
early Danian	0.07158083	0.0566	0.0845	0.0701	0.0710
middle Danian	0.10483342	0.0761	0.1245	0.0995	0.1011

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table S. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Galeomorphii (excluding †Synchodontiformes) using the Stevns Klint regional sub-sample and a three-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Regional three-age time-binning scheme					
late Maastrichtian	0.07433491	0.0526	0.0917	0.0715	0.0728
early Danian	0.06924778	0.0541	0.0815	0.0673	0.0682
middle Danian	0.10923748	0.0736	0.1303	0.1010	0.1028

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table T. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Squalomorphii using the Stevns Klint regional sub-sample and a three-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Regional three-age time-binning scheme					
late Maastrichtian	0.07756513	0.0537	0.0931	0.0728	0.0740
early Danian	0.04105018	0.0312	0.0466	0.0387	0.0392
middle Danian	0.02008752	-0.0101	0.0293	0.0090	0.0102

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table U. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Lamniformes (n=690) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Four-age time-binning scheme					
Campanian	0.06345675	0.0564	0.0696	0.0628	0.0632
Maastrichtian	0.07041109	0.0630	0.0773	0.0699	0.0704
Danian-Selandian	0.05972992	0.0496	0.0685	0.0587	0.0593
Thanetian	0.05562265	0.0451	0.0642	0.0544	0.0550

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table V. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Carcharhiniformes (n=232) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Four-age time-binning scheme					
Campanian	0.08523550	0.0629	0.1026	0.0821	0.0834
Maastrichtian	0.05627971	0.0415	0.0677	0.0542	0.0550
Danian-Selandian	0.04167265	0.0338	0.0485	0.0409	0.0413
Thanetian	0.06197006	0.0509	0.0712	0.0607	0.0614

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table W. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Heterodontiformes (n=23) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Four-age time-binning scheme					
Campanian	0.05642643	0.0175	0.0765	0.0461	0.0480
Maastrichtian	0.04315409	0.0088	0.0664	0.0367	0.0385
Danian-Selandian	0.05059766	0.0114	0.0656	0.0376	0.0394
Thanetian	0.05693581	0.0210	0.0730	0.0462	0.0478

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table X. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Orectolobiformes (n=116) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Four-age time-binning scheme					
Campanian	0.02406313	0.0128	0.0322	0.0222	0.0228
Maastrichtian	0.04110695	0.0290	0.0518	0.0400	0.0408
Danian-Selandian	0.06491247	0.0446	0.0804	0.0619	0.0631
Thanetian	0.05674483	0.0332	0.0744	0.0531	0.0544

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table Y. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Hexanchiformes (n=43) using the three-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Ages					
Maastrichtian	0.01846043	0.0012	0.0286	0.0145	0.0154
Danian-Selandian	0.12424372	0.0672	0.1684	0.1162	0.1194
Thanetian	0.05400864	0.0333	0.0667	0.0495	0.0505

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table Z. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Squaliformes (n=86) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Four-age time-binning scheme					
Campanian	0.07059085	0.0347	0.0948	0.0638	0.0657
Maastrichtian	0.05435441	0.0331	0.0728	0.0523	0.0536
Danian-Selandian	0.03277852	0.0239	0.0395	0.0315	0.0320
Thanetian	0.03350868	-0.0057	0.0506	0.0216	0.0234

PI = Prediction; CI = Confidence.

Table AA. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for Squatiniformes (n=23) using the three-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Ages					
Campanian	0.02448442	0.0098	0.0351	0.0220	0.0228
Maastrichtian	0.01809533	0.0072	0.0219	0.0143	0.0148
Danian-Selandian	0.01412439	0.0038	0.0198	0.0116	0.0121

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table BB. PV and associated interval estimations (95% prediction and confidence limits) for †Synchodontiformes (n=17) using the three-age time-binning scheme. Interval estimates were generated using bootstrapping with 999 iterations.

	Raw Disparity	Lower.PI	Upper.PI	Lower.CI	Upper.CI
Ages					
Campanian	0.0300658	-0.0050	0.0458	0.0196	0.0212
Maastrichtian	0.1000783	-0.0178	0.1490	0.0630	0.0682
Danian-Selandian	0.1283956	0.0583	0.1748	0.1147	0.1184

PI = Prediction, CI = Confidence.

Table CC. Effect of monognathic and dignathic heterodonty on temporal disparity using the four-age time-binning scheme. Pairwise differences between groups (i.e. time-bins) are based on RRPP. Upper off-diagonal cells depict FDR-adjusted *P*-values; lower off-diagonal cells depict raw *P*-values. Bold values indicate significant difference between treatment means at $\alpha=0.05$.

	Disparity Models											
	Shape ~ Position + Time (N=897)				Shape ~ Unit + Time (N=334)				Shape ~ Position + Unit + Time (N=334)			
	C	M	D-S	T	C	M	D-S	T	C	M	D-S	T
C	-	0.371	0.008	0.133	-	0.184	0.016	0.184	-	0.016	0.008	0.027
M	0.232	-	0.032	0.417	0.081	-	0.258	1.000	0.004	-	0.793	0.793
D-S	0.001	0.008	-	0.218	0.002	0.161	-	0.184	0.001	0.548	-	0.468
T	0.050	0.313	0.109	-	0.092	0.901	0.091	-	0.010	0.595	0.234	-

C = Campanian, M = Maastrichtian, D-S = Danian-Selandian, T = Thanetian.

N = Total sample size.

Table DD. PV obtained from models incorporating monognathic and dignathic heterodonty in the four-age time-binning scheme.

	Raw Disparity		
	Monognathic Model	Dignathic Model	Monognathic + Dignathic Model
Four-age time-binning scheme			
Campanian	0.06056318	0.05835967	0.04414708
Maastrichtian	0.06692364	0.07537542	0.06967781
Danian-Selandian	0.08260271	0.09095291	0.07513766
Thanetian	0.07279262	0.07416767	0.06513087

Table EE. Descriptive statistics of temporal distributions using the five-age time-binning scheme. IQR = Interquartile range.

	Skewness				Kurtosis				IQR			
	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4
Campanian	0.200	-0.408	0.246	-0.654	2.704	3.097	2.419	3.875	0.278	0.129	0.124	0.071
Maastrichtian	0.621	-0.080	0.068	-1.610	2.721	2.479	2.571	8.246	0.287	0.158	0.133	0.054
Danian	0.261	0.283	0.440	-0.707	2.351	3.078	3.162	4.949	0.347	0.130	0.115	0.072
Selandian	0.133	-0.052	1.070	-0.030	2.448	2.999	2.857	2.876	0.185	0.103	0.049	0.056
Thanetian	-0.033	0.318	-0.056	-0.731	2.245	2.815	3.330	3.499	0.352	0.114	0.133	0.075

Table FF. Descriptive statistics of temporal distributions using the four-age time-binning scheme. IQR = Interquartile range. IQR = Interquartile range; D-S = Danian-Selandian.

	Skewness				Kurtosis				IQR			
	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4
Campanian	0.200	-0.408	0.246	-0.654	2.704	3.097	2.419	3.875	0.278	0.129	0.124	0.071
Maastrichtian	0.621	-0.080	0.068	-1.610	2.721	2.479	2.571	8.246	0.287	0.158	0.133	0.054
D-S	0.245	0.224	0.350	-0.724	2.303	2.989	2.880	4.982	0.361	0.133	0.124	0.074
Thanetian	-0.033	0.318	-0.056	-0.731	2.245	2.815	3.330	3.499	0.352	0.114	0.133	0.075

Table GG. False discovery rate adjusted p-values obtained from multiple pairwise comparisons between time-bins. Reported statistics correspond to the morphospace analysis of Selachimorpha. Bold values are significant.

	Pairwise <i>P</i> -values between means (Pr > d)				
	PC's (all)	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4
Five-age time-binning scheme	pFDR	pFDR	pFDR	pFDR	pFDR
Campanian: Maastrichtian	0.003	0.025	0.656	0.002	0.246
Campanian: Danian	0.008	0.576	0.008	0.002	0.578
Campanian: Selandian	0.010	0.434	0.009	0.002	0.042
Campanian: Thanetian	0.003	0.063	0.008	0.002	1.000
Maastrichtian: Danian	0.004	0.013	0.015	0.008	0.098
Maastrichtian: Selandian	0.003	1.000	0.010	0.002	0.042
Maastrichtian: Thanetian	0.003	0.013	0.008	0.074	0.504
Danian: Selandian	0.007	0.298	0.123	0.002	0.098
Danian: Thanetian	0.210	0.298	0.656	0.634	0.578
Selandian: Thanetian	0.003	0.100	0.209	0.002	0.042
Four-age time-binning scheme					
Campanian: Maastrichtian	0.002	0.011	0.878	0.002	0.364
Campanian: Danian-Selandian	0.006	0.807	0.002	0.002	0.364
Campanian: Thanetian	0.002	0.040	0.002	0.002	1.000
Maastrichtian: Danian-Selandian	0.002	0.008	0.002	0.002	0.032
Maastrichtian: Thanetian	0.002	0.008	0.002	0.080	0.485
Danian-Selandian: Thanetian	0.069	0.123	0.999	0.139	0.364
Regional subsample					
late Maastrichtian: early Danian	1.000	1.000	1	1.000	0.354
late Maastrichtian: middle Danian	0.002	0.005	1	0.007	0.167
early Danian: middle Danian	0.002	0.005	1	0.007	0.354

Table HH. False discovery rate adjusted p-values obtained from multiple pairwise comparisons between time-bins. Reported statistics correspond to the temporal morphospace analysis of Galeomorphii (including †Synchodontiformes). Bold values are significant.

	Pairwise <i>P</i> -values between means (Pr > d)				
	PC's (all)	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4
Four-age time-binning scheme					
Campanian: Maastrichtian	0.001	0.204	0.034	0.001	0.010
Campanian: Danian-Selandian	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.066	0.033
Campanian: Thanetian	0.002	0.005	0.002	0.002	0.951
Maastrichtian: Danian-Selandian	0.001	0.001	0.026	0.001	0.001
Maastrichtian: Thanetian	0.001	0.001	0.114	0.004	0.037
Danian-Selandian: Thanetian	0.269	0.441	0.595	0.084	0.066
Stevens Klint regional sub-sample					
late Maastrichtian: early Danian	0.475	0.520	0.691	0.120	0.342
late Maastrichtian: middle Danian	0.007	0.019	0.636	0.001	0.060
early Danian: middle Danian	0.002	0.002	0.376	0.008	0.232

Table II. False discovery rate adjusted *p*-values obtained from multiple pairwise comparisons between time-bins. Reported statistics correspond to the morphospace analysis of Squalomorphii. Bold values are significant.

Four-age time-binning scheme	Pairwise <i>P</i> -values between means ($Pr > d$)				
	PC's (all)	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4
Campanian: Maastrichtian	0.004	0.048	0.083	1.000	0.168
Campanian: Danian-Selandian	0.211	0.240	1.000	0.339	0.376
Campanian: Thanetian	0.014	0.093	0.136	0.088	1.000
Maastrichtian: Danian-Selandian	0.005	0.093	0.016	0.184	0.389
Maastrichtian: Thanetian	0.004	0.931	0.008	0.016	0.172
Danian-Selandian: Thanetian	0.082	0.462	0.084	0.212	0.389

Table JJ. PC1–PC4 pairwise comparisons between time-bins for Lamniformes (N=660) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Raw and FDR-adjusted *P*-values are provided. Bold values indicate significant difference between treatment means at $\alpha=0.05$.

Treatments	Pairwise <i>P</i> -values between means ($Pr > d$)									
	PC's (all)		PC1		PC2		PC3		PC4	
	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR
C:M	0.008	0.013	0.751	1.000	0.157	0.251	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.008
C: D-S	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.004	0.249	0.398	0.331	0.530
C: T	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.031	0.062	0.001	0.002	0.003	0.012
M: D-S	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.002	0.009	0.024
M: T	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.280	0.373	0.335	0.447	0.693	0.924
D-S: T	0.054	0.072	0.558	0.893	0.029	0.062	0.001	0.002	0.078	0.156

C = Campanian, M = Maastrichtian, D-S = Danian-Selandian, T = Thanetian.

Table KK. PC1–PC4 pairwise comparisons between time-bins for Carcharhiniformes (N=228) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Raw and FDR-adjusted *P*-values are provided. Bold values indicate significant difference between treatment means at $\alpha=0.05$.

Treatments	Pairwise <i>P</i> -values between means ($Pr > d$)									
	PC's (all)		PC1		PC2		PC3		PC4	
	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR
C:M	0.067	0.134	0.095	0.253	0.154	0.308	0.091	0.243	0.243	0.616
C: D-S	0.002	0.016	0.003	0.024	0.031	0.124	0.810	1.000	0.308	0.616
C: T	0.054	0.134	0.284	0.509	0.007	0.056	0.391	0.243	0.524	0.838
M: D-S	0.140	0.187	0.318	0.509	0.607	0.809	0.083	0.243	0.012	0.096
M: T	0.119	0.187	0.407	0.543	0.122	0.308	0.009	0.072	0.047	0.188
D-S: T	0.019	0.076	0.041	0.164	0.216	0.346	0.198	0.396	0.716	0.955

C = Campanian, M = Maastrichtian, D-S = Danian-Selandian, T = Thanetian.

Table LL. PC1–PC4 pairwise comparisons between time-bins for Heterodontiformes (N=23) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Raw and FDR-adjusted P -values are provided. Bold values indicate significant difference between treatment means at $\alpha=0.05$.

Treatments	Pairwise P -values between means ($Pr > d$)									
	PC's (all)		PC1		PC2		PC3		PC4	
	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR
C:M	0.315	1	0.335	1	0.186	0.744	0.334	1	0.299	1
C: D-S	0.545	1	0.640	1	0.073	0.584	0.756	1	0.501	1
C: T	0.838	1	0.794	1	0.375	0.774	0.824	1	0.758	1
M: D-S	0.856	1	0.722	1	0.559	0.894	0.612	1	0.788	1
M: T	0.581	1	0.474	1	0.735	0.980	0.434	1	0.475	1
D-S: T	0.906	1	0.824	1	0.387	0.774	0.876	1	0.730	1

C = Campanian, M = Maastrichtian, D-S = Danian-Selandian, T = Thanetian.

Table MM. PC1–PC4 pairwise comparisons between time-bins for Orectolobiformes (N=116) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Raw and FDR-adjusted P -values are provided. Bold values indicate significant difference between treatment means at $\alpha=0.05$.

Treatments	Pairwise P -values between means ($Pr > d$)									
	PC's (all)		PC1		PC2		PC3		PC4	
	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR
C:M	0.156	0.250	0.670	1.000	0.043	0.115	0.081	0.216	0.036	0.072
C: D-S	0.010	0.080	0.083	0.221	0.028	0.112	0.011	0.088	0.001	0.008
C: T	0.065	0.173	0.908	1.000	0.013	0.104	0.031	0.124	0.006	0.024
M: D-S	0.048	0.173	0.077	0.221	0.559	0.894	0.154	0.308	0.018	0.048
M: T	0.500	0.667	0.605	1.000	0.338	0.676	0.261	0.418	0.173	0.277
D-S: T	0.105	0.210	0.080	0.221	0.710	0.947	0.945	1.000	0.547	0.729

C = Campanian, M = Maastrichtian, D-S = Danian-Selandian, T = Thanetian.

Table NN. PC1–PC4 pairwise comparisons between time-bins for Hexanchiformes (N=40) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Raw and FDR-adjusted P -values are provided. Bold values indicate significant difference between treatment means at $\alpha=0.05$.

Treatments	Pairwise P -values between means ($Pr > d$)									
	PC's (all)		PC1		PC2		PC3		PC4	
	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR
M: D-S	0.047	0.212	0.090	0.405	0.436	0.981	0.011	0.050	0.056	0.252
M: T	0.201	0.452	0.219	0.493	0.329	0.981	0.141	0.291	0.203	0.457
D-S: T	0.559	0.838	0.621	0.932	0.729	1.000	0.194	0.291	0.473	0.710

M = Maastrichtian, D-S = Danian-Selandian, T = Thanetian.

Table OO. PC1–PC4 pairwise comparisons between time-bins for Squaliformes (N=86) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Raw and FDR-adjusted P -values are provided. Bold values indicate significant difference between treatment means at $\alpha=0.05$.

Treatments	Pairwise P -values between means ($Pr > d$)									
	PC's (all)		PC1		PC2		PC3		PC4	
	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR
C:M	0.030	0.120	0.055	0.220	0.102	0.816	0.758	1.000	0.054	0.216
C: D-S	0.321	0.856	0.824	1.000	0.300	0.982	0.097	0.388	0.863	1.000
C: T	0.681	1.000	0.347	0.778	0.925	1.000	0.618	1.000	0.643	1.000
M: D-S	0.013	0.104	0.019	0.152	0.491	0.982	0.046	0.368	0.016	0.128
M: T	0.771	1.000	0.953	1.000	0.412	0.982	0.747	1.000	0.127	0.339
D-S: T	0.764	1.000	0.389	0.778	0.629	1.000	0.630	1.000	0.526	1.000

C = Campanian, M = Maastrichtian, D-S = Danian-Selandian, T = Thanetian.

Table PP. PC1–PC4 pairwise comparisons between time-bins for Squatiniformes (N=86) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Raw and FDR-adjusted *P*-values are provided. Bold values indicate significant difference between treatment means at $\alpha=0.05$.

	Pairwise <i>P</i> -values between means ($Pr > d$)									
	PC's (all)		PC1		PC2		PC3		PC4	
	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR
C: M	0.115	0.518	0.394	0.887	0.022	0.099	0.726	1.000	0.185	0.711
C: D-S	0.395	0.592	0.859	1.000	0.241	0.542	0.030	0.135	0.878	1.000
M: D-S	0.388	0.592	0.363	0.887	0.369	0.554	0.153	0.344	0.316	0.711

C = Campanian, M = Maastrichtian, D-S = Danian-Selandian.

Table QQ. PC1–PC4 pairwise comparisons between time-bins for †Synechodontiformes (N=16) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Raw and FDR-adjusted *P*-values are provided. Bold values indicate significant difference between treatment means at $\alpha=0.05$.

	Pairwise <i>P</i> -values between means ($Pr > d$)									
	PC's (all)		PC1		PC2		PC3		PC4	
	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR	<i>P</i>	FDR
C: M	0.602	1	0.506	1	0.966	1.000	0.857	1	0.857	1
C: D-S	0.373	1	0.346	1	0.295	0.767	0.664	1	0.986	1
M: D-S	0.898	1	0.952	1	0.341	0.767	0.788	1	0.794	1

C = Campanian, M = Maastrichtian, D-S = Danian-Selandian.

Table RR. Lagerstätten effects on disparity in Selachimorpha (N=1045) using the four-age time-binning scheme. PV and pairwise statistics are provided. Upper off-diagonal cells depict FDR-adjusted *P*-values; lower off-diagonal cells depict raw *P*-values. Bold values indicate significant difference between treatment means at $\alpha=0.05$.

Four-age time-binning scheme	Raw Disparity	Pairwise comparisons among time-bins			
		Campanian	Maastrichtian	D-S	Thanetian
Campanian	0.06911023	-	0.547	0.181	0.040
Maastrichtian	0.07331670	0.397	-	0.547	0.181
D-S	0.07980210	0.068	0.284	-	0.547
Thanetian	0.08535443	0.005	0.047	0.410	-

D-S = Danian-Selandian.

Table SS. False discovery rate adjusted p-values obtained from multiple pairwise comparisons between time-bins. Sensitivity analysis excluding the Stevens Klint regional sub-sample (N=1045) and a four-age time-binning scheme.

Four-age time-binning scheme	Pairwise <i>P</i> -values between means ($Pr > d$)				
	PC's (all)	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4
	pFDR	pFDR	pFDR	pFDR	pFDR
Maastrichtian: Danian-Selandian	0.002	0.004	0.004	0.002	0.632

Table TT. Non-parametric multivariate analysis of variance with RRPP testing of monognathic heterodonty on morphospace(N=932). Coefficient estimation via ordinary least squares (OLS). Type I (sequential) sums of squares were used to calculate sums of squares and cross-products matrices. Effect sizes (Z) are based on F distribution.

	<i>d.f.</i>	SS	MS	R^2	F	Z	Pr(>F)
All PC-axes							
~ tooth positions	3	11.066	3.6886	0.14037	50.511	7.4612	0.001**
PC1							
~ tooth positions	3	10.078	3.3592	0.20297	78.772	4.7538	0.001**
PC2							
~ tooth positions	3	0.0640	0.021337	0.00666	2.0734	1.1592	0.097
PC3							
~ tooth positions	3	0.7135	0.23783	0.08788	29.804	3.7889	0.001**
PC4							
~ tooth positions	3	0.1619	0.053969	0.04492	14.548	3.2897	0.001**

Abbreviations: *d.f.* = degrees of freedom; SS = sequential sums of squares; MS = Mean squares; F statistics = F value by permutation; R^2 = coefficient of determination; Z = effect size. P -values are based on 999 permutations.

Table UU. PC1–PC4 pairwise comparisons sensitivity analysis of monognathic heterodonty. Raw and FDR-adjusted P -values are provided. Bold values indicate significant difference between treatment means at $\alpha=0.05$.

Tooth positions	Pairwise P -values between means (Pr > d)							
	PC1		PC2		PC3		PC4	
	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR
parasymphyseal: anterior	0.838	1.000	0.906	1.000	0.823	1.000	0.005	0.010
parasymphyseal: lateroposterior	0.002	0.003	0.718	1.000	0.002	0.005	0.001	0.004
parasymphyseal: posterior	0.001	0.002	0.107	0.285	0.036	0.072	0.005	0.010
anterior: lateroposterior	0.001	0.002	0.524	1.000	0.001	0.005	0.001	0.004
anterior: posterior	0.001	0.002	0.011	0.088	0.002	0.005	0.298	0.397
lateroposterior: posterior	0.001	0.002	0.030	0.12	0.390	0.624	0.134	0.214

Table VV. PC1–PC4 pairwise comparisons sensitivity analysis of dignathic heterodonty. Raw and FDR-adjusted P -values are provided. Bold values indicate significant difference between treatment means at $\alpha=0.05$.

Dental units	Pairwise P -values between means (Pr > d)							
	PC1		PC2		PC3		PC4	
	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR	P	FDR
lower: upper	0.329	0.658	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.28	0.56

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Figure A. Geographic distribution, sample percentages and proportions in our global Selachimorpha dataset. (A) Pie charts depict sample provenance and chronostratigraphic age. (B) Sample counts and percentages for each geographic region. (C–D) Order-level clade counts and percentages for each global four-age time-bin and region. Map was generated using the *maps* [9] and *ggplot2* [10] packages. Silhouettes generated by M.B.

Figure B. Phylogenetic framework and landmark scheme. (A) Phylogenetic topology illustrating our order-level clad taxonomy. (B) Geometric morphometric landmark-scheme showing fixed type 1 and type 2 landmarks (red) versus sliding semi-landmarks (open circles). LM=landmarks. Silhouettes generated by M.B.

Figure C. Bar plots of labial and lingual tooth views. Based on the four-age time-binning scheme.

Figure D. Resampled and scaled points. Outlines show increasing point numbers up to the optimal 160 points ($curve_1=79$, $curve_2=81$). Curve end-points (LM1, LM80, and LM160) were treated as geometrically homologous landmarks.

Figure E. Landmark visualizations. Lamniformes (*Cretalamna maroccana*); Carcharhiniformes (*Danogaleus gueriri*); Orectolobiformes (*Plicatoscyllium lehneri*); Heterodontiformes (*Heterodontus granti*); Hexanchiformes (*Notidanodon dentatus*); Squaliformes (*Proetmopterus hemmooriensis*); Echinorhiniformes (*Echinorhinus maremagnum*); Squatiniformes (*Squatina* sp); †Synechodontiformes (*Synechodus filipi*). Aspect ratio=1.

Figure F. Sliding performance of semi-landmarks under different iterations. Convergence required only 6 iterations. Consensus configurations from iterations >6 suffered from drift indicating no improvement in alignment solution. Red lines indicate maximum and minimum Q-values.

Figure G. Henze-Zirkler's multivariate normality test of Procrustes-aligned coordinates. (A) Chi-square and (B) adjusted chi-square Q-Q plot for multivariate outliers based on Mahalanobis distance.

Figure H. Locality map and lithostratigraphical units spanning the Maastrichtian–Danian boundary at Stevns Klint in Denmark. (A) Map of Denmark and the municipality of Stevns in Sjælland. (B–C) Højerup. (D–E) Korsnæb Odde, near Rødvig. Map was generated using the *mapDK* package [11]. Images (B–E) courtesy Jesper Milan (Geomuseum Faxe).

Figure I. Mean shape comparisons from the first and second digitization (N=30). Specimen information is given in Table G.

Figure J. Two-block partial least squares (2B-PLS) analysis. Results indicate strong association between digitization's, and thus, minimal measurement error.

Figure K. Summary statistics from principal component analysis. Proportion of variance by component (PC1–PC10) and cumulative proportion of variance.

Deformation isolines using Thin Plate Splines

Figure L. Hypothetical morphologies corresponding to the minimum and maximum values of PC1–PC4. (A–D) Isolines and counter lines based on the TPS-method. Areas of concentrated strain are indicated by increasing red intensity and represents the amount of change at any given location [3].

Figure M. Global shark rarefaction profiles. Based on the five-age time-binning scheme. CI = Confidence Intervals.

Figure N. Estimates of disparity considering categorical predictor variables. See supplementary text for model descriptions.

Figure O. Global morphospace time-series. (A-B) Jittered box-plots visualizing distribution on PC1/PC2 using the four-age time-binning scheme. Arithmetic mean with 95% confidence limits was derived from non-parametric bootstrapping; modal value and medians are shown for each level. TPS-grids indicate changes in the modal PC-value between ages time-bins.

Figure P. Morphospace dynamics. Box-plots illustrate lamniform (Anacoracidae) versus hexanchiform (Chlamydoselachidae, Heptanchidae, Hexanchidae, Orthacodontidae) distribution in the Maastrichtian and Danian-Selandian time-bins.

Figure Q. Taxonomic composition and geographic distribution of Selandian genus-level occurrences. Most samples represent lamniforms from the Orp-le-Grand locality in Belgium.

Figure R. Sub-age disparity. (A–C) Global disparity profiles for the superorder-level clades Selachimorpha, Galeomorphii, and Squalomorphii.

Figure S. Global morphospace time-series analysis. (A–B) Distribution of morphology along PC3/PC4 using the five-age time-binning scheme. Arithmetic mean with 95% confidence limits was derived from non-parametric bootstrapping; modal value and medians are shown for each level. TPS-grids indicate changes in the modal PC-value between ages.

Figure U. Box-and-whisker plot morphospace visualization of monognathic heterodonty. (A–D) Distribution and computed 95% confidence intervals for standardized tooth positions (parasympyseal=26, anterior=270, lateroposterior=578, posterior=58) along PC1–PC4. Significant FDR-adjusted p-values for multiple comparisons are indicated.

Figure V. Box-and-whisker plot morphospace visualization of dignathic heterodonty. (A–D) Distribution and computed 95% confidence intervals for dental units (lower=189, upper=176) along PC1–PC4. Significant FDR-adjusted p-values for multiple comparisons are indicated.

Figure W. Standardized monognathic heterodont tooth positions for order-level clades along PC1–PC4. Silhouettes generated by MB.

Figure X. Standardized dignathic heterodont tooth positions for order-level clades along PC1-PC4. Silhouettes generated by MB.

Figure Y. Effects of dignathic heterodonty. Morphospace analysis based on dental units (N=310) using the five-age time-binning scheme.

Figure Z. Effects of dignathic heterodonty. Morphospace analysis based on dental units (N=334) using the four-age time-binning scheme.

Figure AA. Effects of monognathic heterodonty. Morphospace analysis based on standardized tooth positions (N=858) using the five-age time-binning scheme. Intermediate tooth positions omitted.

Figure BB. Effects of monognathic heterodonty. Morphospace analysis based on standardized tooth positions (N=897) using the four-age time-binning scheme. Intermediate tooth positions omitted.

Figure CC. Sensitivity analysis. (A) Differences in morphospace occupation between lingual and labial views. **(B–C)** OLS-regression showing the linear relationship between scores.

Figure DD. Results of linear regression models. (A–H) Relationship between lingual and labial views partitioned into order-level clades.

SUPPLEMENTARY REFERENCES

1. Arnqvist G, Mårtensson T. Measurement error in geometric morphometrics: Empirical strategies to assess and reduce its impact on measures of shape. *Acta Zool Acad Sci Hungaricae*. 1998.
2. Fruciano C. Measurement error in geometric morphometrics. *Dev Genes Evol*. 2016;226: 139–158. doi:10.1007/s00427-016-0537-4
3. Claude J. *Morphometrics with R*. Springer Science & Business Media; 2008. Available: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/258885233>
4. Cappetta H. *Handbook of Paleoichthyology Volume 3E: Chondrichthyes - Mesozoic and Cenozoic Elasmobranchii: Teeth*. Munich, Germany: Verlag Dr. Friedrich Pfeil; 2012.
5. Bazzi M, Kear BP, Blom H, Ahlberg PE, Campione NE. Static Dental Disparity and Morphological Turnover in Sharks across the End-Cretaceous Mass Extinction. *Curr Biol*. 2018. doi:10.1016/j.cub.2018.05.093
6. Siverson M. A new large lamniform shark from the uppermost Gearle Siltstone (Cenomanian, Late Cretaceous) of Western Australia. *Trans R Soc Edinburgh, Earth Sci*. 1999;90: 49–66. doi:10.1017/S0263593300002509
7. Shimada K. Dentition of the late cretaceous lamniform shark, *Cretoxyrhina mantelli* from the Niobrara chalk of Kansas. *J Vertebr Paleontol*. 1997;17: 269–279. doi:10.1080/02724634.1997.10010974
8. Bookstein FL. *Morphometric Tools for Landmark Data. Morphometric Tools for Landmark Data*. Cambridge University Press; 1991. doi:10.1017/cbo9780511573064
9. Brownrigg R. *maps: Draw Geographical Maps*. 2018. Available: <https://cran.r-project.org/package=maps>
10. Wickham H. *ggplot2 Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series A (Statistics in Society)*. 2016. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-24277-4
11. Barfort S. *mapDK: Maps of Denmark*. 2015.